

ORGANIZING FOREIGN LANGUAGES ATMOSPHERE AND MANAGEMENT IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Safarova Nurxon Abdusamat qizi

TDPU magistranti

+998933243883

nurxoneshonqulova@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10506092>

Abstract. Article will describe some aspects of organizing foreign language atmosphere in higher education and managing pedagogic process. Moreover, advantages of providing modern innovative technologies and programs in teaching English language, boost learners' foreign language competence. Enhance students' communication in foreign language.

Key words: management, foreign language atmosphere, teaching methods, language competence, communication, modern technologies, teaching programs.

ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ ИНОСТРАННОЙ ЯЗЫКОВОЙ АТМОСФЕРЫ И МЕНЕДЖМЕНТА В ВЫСШЕМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ

Аннотация. В статье будут описаны некоторые аспекты организации иноязычной атмосферы в высшей школе и управления педагогическим процессом. Более того, преимущества предоставления современных инновационных технологий и программ в обучении английскому языку повышают компетентность учащихся в иностранном языке. Улучшить общение учащихся на иностранном языке.

Ключевые слова: менеджмент, иноязычная атмосфера, методы обучения, языковая компетенция, коммуникация, современные технологии, программы обучения.

It is certainly true that organizing foreign language atmosphere and provide modern technologies and programs in higher education is one of the most important task of modern manager. Therefore, youngsters are demanded to be competitive in foreign language to get worldwide information and explore the science more. In order to create modern phenomenon we explored some researches that study focused on how lesson planning takes place at the high level in contrast to how the process takes place in grades 1 through the second. The study was conducted through a survey and interviews to English professors at the universities of General Studies at the University. In order to conduct the research, factors such as academic background, teaching experience, context, age, teaching practices, motivation, and syllabus design were considered.

According to collected data planning does take place at the higher level, first in the form of a semester-long syllabus and then in daily/weekly lesson plans that include varying degrees of detail. Lesson planning helps improve teacher performance by providing confidence. It improves student learning outcomes by helping them better understand the materials. Both, teachers and students, benefit from the focus and guidance planning provides. And also some recommendations include creating teacher training programs in institutions of higher educations to provide the support teachers need to perform at their best and conducting further research in

other departments, colleges, or campuses to see how planning takes places outside English courses.¹

Oftentimes it is the foreign language classroom that provides the basic foundation for language exposure and acquisition. In the context of the foreign language classroom there is not much exposure to the TL outside of this setting. This being the case, the quantity of the TL should be relatively high as it is an essential requisite for language acquisition. In addition, most recent research tends to suggest that high quantities of TL from the instructor is ideal. The main purpose of this study has been to focus on university-level foreign language classrooms to explore the issue of language choice, LI or TL, among instructors.

Analysis of the data revealed a much different pattern: Story-reading alone actually produced the lowest score gains, while the two treatments involving exercises produced gains that were similarly high. Apparently, vocabulary exercises combined with a short story provided the extra context and practice the subjects needed to learn those words better than did story reading alone. Vocabulary exercises alone produced better scores than story reading alone perhaps because the subjects were accustomed to the task of learning vocabulary words through exercises, and because the task (learning words) was obvious. The subjects were probably not accustomed to learning words simply through reading stories, nor was the task of learning words obvious in that case. Thus, given the special parameters of this study and its subjects, score gains were lowest on the treatment that was expected to produce the highest gains. In addition, some of the findings reveal a learning and teaching environment that prevents strategies from addressing linguistic, social and cultural development with a coherent workable vision in the English classroom.

Because English is the working language of government, business, and industry, an English-only policy seems to be a practical means to prepare students for higher education and the workforce. The growing status of English as an international lingual provides additional support for such a policy.

This study reveals the need to rethink the imposition of an English-only policy. The findings indicate that current teaching approaches, methods and materials do not entirely support language development in English, largely because they do not take into account the economic, social, and linguistic situations of the students.

There is a critical need for college students to receive an education that fosters global learning in preparation for life in an increasingly interdependent and interconnected world. Universities recognize this need and endeavor to provide a range of programs that target global knowledge and skills, and meet the needs of traditional and non-traditional students. Domestic foreign language immersion programs can contribute to student global learning and development by providing students with an opportunity to participate in a rich global learning experience in the U.S. While some researchers have investigated impacts of domestic foreign language immersion on language proficiency, few studies of other kinds of global learning outcomes are available, and research is needed to gain an understanding of program impacts and make

¹ Hessel, Gianna. "The impact of participation in ERASMUS study abroad in the UK on students' overall English language proficiency, self-efficacy, English use anxiety and self-motivation to continue learning English : a mixed-methods investigation." Thesis, University of Oxford, 2016.

improvements. The purpose of this study was to determine the extent to which participation in a domestic foreign language immersion program was perceived to influence global learning and development. The study used a mixed-methods design that incorporated as a key instrument a retrospective survey of former participants in a university-level domestic foreign language immersion program. Perspectives from short-term study abroad, foreign languages, transformative learning, and global citizenship informed the research. The study found that participants in a domestic foreign language immersion program perceived influence in all three domains of global development.

Moreover, effectiveness of using computer technology and the Internet to enhance classroom teaching. A variety of computer and internet based projects that complement lessons initiated by the classroom teacher provide real life situations for additional practice, reinforcement, motivation and greater student achievement.

English is not the dominant language, language schools are available to assist in the acquisition of the language. It is stated that EFL methods are effective and thriving in teaching English to non-native speakers. It is further pointed out that EFL methods rival those used in traditional classes which mainly use teacher-orientated-language whereas TEFL focuses on enhancing student-orientated-language in a classroom. The research's importance stems from the area of focus and purpose. It is the primary purpose of this paper to examine whether improved possibilities and imperatives of language acquisition to subjects and teachers are offered by TEFL methods. ²The dissertation derives greater primary importance upon consideration of the effectiveness of TEFL in multi-lingual classrooms. This dissertation will determine whether EFL methods are in fact more effective and efficient in teaching English than other known methods. On another point it should then be possible to improve TEFL methods and take them to further possibilities such as online classes or web-based-training. The dissertation's aim is to critically review TEFL as an effective method of teaching English in a multi-lingual environment. This is done by incorporating the TEFL teaching methods into an experimental classroom of students from different ethnical backgrounds, age groups and mother tongues – except English.

REFERENCES

1. Hessel, Gianna. "The impact of participation in ERASMUS study abroad in the UK on students' overall English language proficiency, self-efficacy, English use anxiety and self-motivation to continue learning English: a mixed-methods investigation." Thesis, University of Oxford, 2016.
2. Zhang, Yun. "Teachers' Self-Efficacy Beliefs In Relation To Perceived English Proficiency And Teaching Practices: An Investigation Of Chinese Primary English As A Foreign Language (Efl) Teachers." Scholarly Commons, 2019.
3. Pak, Samuel Sungchoon. "Incorporating crosscultural learning strategies to reduce English language learning stresses on Hong Kong's secondary students." CSUSB ScholarWorks, 1999.

² Zhang, Yun. "TEACHERS' SELF-EFFICACY BELIEFS IN RELATION TO PERCEIVED ENGLISH PROFICIENCY AND TEACHING PRACTICES: AN INVESTIGATION OF CHINESE PRIMARY ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE (EFL) TEACHERS." Scholarly Commons, 2019.

4. Mitchell, Peter. "The impact of the storyline method on the foreign language classroom: an action research case study with military linguist cadets." Thesis, University of Derby, 2016
5. Sedibe, Godwin Konotia Bully. "The achievement gap between learners who are assessed in a primary language and those assessed in a non-primary language in the natural sciences learning area." Thesis, Stellenbosch: University of Stellenbosch, 2009